

COMORBID PRIMARY OPEN-ANGLE GLAUCOMA AND DRY AMD: SYNERGISTIC RETINAL DEGENERATION AND TREATMENT STRATEGIES

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To compare the morphofunctional characteristics of isolated POAG, dry AMD, and their comorbid form, and to evaluate the effectiveness of various therapeutic strategies, including neuroprotective and antioxidant therapy

Background. Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) and dry age-related macular degeneration (AMD) are leading causes of irreversible vision loss in the elderly. While traditionally studied in isolation, their comorbid presentation is increasingly common and may accelerate structural and functional deterioration of the retina and optic nerve.

Objective. To compare the morphofunctional characteristics of isolated POAG, dry AMD, and their comorbid form, and to evaluate the effectiveness of various therapeutic strategies, including neuroprotective and antioxidant therapy.

Methods. A prospective, comparative-analytical clinical study was conducted over 12 months and included 168 patients (291 eyes) aged 60–82 years. Participants were divided into three groups: POAG only (n=46), dry AMD only (n=44), and POAG + AMD (n=78). Group 3 was further subdivided by therapy type: prostaglandins (3a), α 2-agonist (3b), and combined α 2-agonist + AREDS 2 (3c). All patients underwent full ophthalmologic evaluation including OCT, OCT-A, perimetry, and mfERG.

Results. A total of 168 patients (291 eyes) were enrolled and distributed into three groups: Group 1 – patients with isolated POAG (n=46), Group 2 – patients with isolated dry AMD (n=44), and Group 3 – patients with comorbid POAG and dry AMD (n=78). The mean age was $69,7 \pm 5,4$ years, with female predominance (58,3%) across all groups. There were no statistically significant differences between the groups in terms of age or gender ($p > 0,05$), ensuring comparability.

Quantitative OCT analysis revealed significantly greater structural damage in the comorbid group (Group 3). Specifically: RNFL thickness was thinnest in Group 3 ($79,6 \pm 10,5$ μ m), compared to POAG ($84,1 \pm 9,8$ μ m) and AMD ($97,2 \pm 7,4$ μ m) ($p < 0,05$). Ganglion cell layer (GCL) thickness followed a similar pattern: $70,5 \pm 8,1$ μ m in Group 3, $75,3 \pm 7,6$ μ m in Group 1,

ABSTRACT

Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) and dry age-related macular degeneration (AMD) are leading causes of irreversible vision loss in the elderly. While traditionally studied in isolation, their comorbid presentation is increasingly common and may accelerate structural and functional deterioration of the retina and optic nerves.

and $82,9 \pm 6,2 \mu\text{m}$ in Group 2 ($p < 0,05$). Macular thickness was lowest in comorbid patients ($238,9 \pm 17,3 \mu\text{m}$), compared to POAG ($262,4 \pm 15,5 \mu\text{m}$) and AMD ($248,1 \pm 14,8 \mu\text{m}$). Subfoveal choroidal thickness was significantly reduced in Group 3 ($170,2 \pm 22,1 \mu\text{m}$) versus Group 1 ($203,6 \pm 24,4 \mu\text{m}$) and Group 2 ($187,3 \pm 20,6 \mu\text{m}$, $p < 0,05$). These data suggest a synergistic structural atrophy in patients with both diseases, affecting not only the macula but also peripapillary and ganglion cell layers.

Visual field assessment confirmed the functional severity of comorbidity: Mean deviation (MD) was significantly worse in Group 3 ($-5,4 \pm 2,3 \text{ dB}$) compared to Group 1 ($-3,1 \pm 1,8 \text{ dB}$) and Group 2 ($-2,2 \pm 1,6 \text{ dB}$, $p < 0,05$). Visual Field Index (VFI) was also lowest in comorbid patients ($78,6 \pm 8,9\%$), with higher values in Group 1 ($89,4 \pm 6,7\%$) and Group 2 ($92,1 \pm 5,5\%$). Group 3 was further stratified by treatment type. After 12 months, patients receiving combined therapy with $\alpha 2$ -agonist + AREDS 2 (Group 3c) showed the most favorable outcomes: Reduction in IOP was greatest in Group 3c ($-4,4 \pm 1,1 \text{ mmHg}$), followed by Group 3b ($-4,2 \pm 1,3 \text{ mmHg}$) and 3a ($-3,1 \pm 1,2 \text{ mmHg}$, $p = 0,002$). GCL thinning over 12 months was least in 3c ($-2,4 \pm 1,6 \mu\text{m}$) versus 3b ($-3,2 \pm 1,5 \mu\text{m}$) and 3a ($-5,6 \pm 1,9 \mu\text{m}$, $p < 0,05$). Macular thinning followed the same trend, with minimal reduction in Group 3c ($-5,1 \pm 2,8 \mu\text{m}$). VFI stability ($< 5\%$ loss) was highest in the combination therapy group (86% of eyes), compared to 79% in 3b and 63% in 3a ($p = 0,01$). Adverse events were also least frequent in Group 3c (7,1%) vs. 3b (12,5%) and 3a (26,9%). These results support the superiority of combination therapy in preserving structural and functional parameters in patients with comorbid POAG and AMD.

Conclusion. Comorbid POAG and dry AMD is associated with synergistic neurodegeneration and more rapid functional decline. Choroidal and macular thinning may serve as predictive markers of progression. Combined therapy with $\alpha 2$ -agonists and AREDS 2 shows potential as an effective treatment strategy in this high-risk population.